

WACŁAW KORABIEWICZ'S COLLECTION OF ETHIOPIAN CROSSES AS A REPRESENTATION OF POLISH COLLECTIONS OF ETHIOPIAN ARTEFACTS¹

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Introduction

The aim of this article is to present one of the biggest world collections of Ethiopian crosses and the man who was responsible for it – a Polish medical doctor Waław Korabiewicz who devoted much of his life to revealing the complicated system of symbolism of the crosses. Over the decades Waław Korabiewicz collaborated with different museums around the world. However, it was the National Museum in Warsaw (Muzeum Narodowe w Warszawie (MNW)) and its collection of Ethiopian crosses which Korabiewicz partly donated, partly offered as a perpetual deposit, which were the most important for the collector and to which he had the most emotional connection. This collection is today one of the biggest among the world collections of Ethiopian crosses, and also one of the most interesting. Apart from being a collector, Korabiewicz's ambition and great passion was research on the symbolism of a cross. His findings, especially in terms of classification of Ethiopian crosses and meanings of the symbolism of their elements, feature in literature dealing with the subject.

Waław Korabiewicz and his work

Waław Korabiewicz was born in 1903 and died in 1994.² He was a medical doctor by profession, who spent many years working in different African countries. From his early years Korabiewicz wanted to travel, so his first choice was a maritime college. However, as a consequence of his bad sight he was not accepted, which made him decide to study medicine at Stefan Batory University in Vilnius and thus to follow the careers of his father and grandfather, who were also medical doctors. At the university Korabiewicz additionally attended courses on ethnography in the Department of Ethnography run by Cezaria Baudouin de Courtenay Ehrenkreutz Jędrzejewiczowa, a distinguished ethnographer who was the first in Poland to introduce phenomenology to studies on folk cultures (Barański, 2010 pp. 54, 65, 331). Jędrzejewiczowa's approach influenced Korabiewicz's attitude towards the objects which he was to collect in the future (Bryzek, 2014 p. 49).

In order to fulfil his dreams, Korabiewicz combined his medical career with his passion for travelling. This resulted in spending long periods in African countries as well as in developing an interest in African art. Eventually Waclaw Korabiewicz started collecting different objects of art and craft which turned him into one of the most acknowledged Polish collectors. As he did not have any grants or donations to fulfil his work as an ethnographer, he funded his activity from his own resources (i.e. his salary as a medical doctor) and from his emoluments from different museums for which he obtained the artefacts (Bryzek, 2014).

Korabiewicz was an interesting personality, living the life of a globetrotter and being a popular writer who authored circa thirty books,³ the majority of them on Africa.⁴ Apart from memoirs of his African experiences and a number of books on other topics, Korabiewicz also tried to describe the phenomenon of Ethiopian crosses, to systematise knowledge on the subject and to search for answers regarding the origins of the symbol of a cross. In Ethiopia he collected not only artefacts, but also – which was of great importance – orally transmitted traditions relating to the crosses and to the symbolical meaning of their different elements. In one of his books he describes how he went about his collecting. He wrote about what was offered in Merkato market in Addis Ababa (mostly ‘rubbish for tourists’, Korabiewicz, 1970 p. 36) and how it was still possible to find rarities. He advised: “do not look at the rubbish for tourists if you are clever, but instead kowtow to the old merchants, talk to them patiently that you are their best friend, ask them to show you old, authentic things. If you are born under a lucky star, they will open sesames for you, and then an old cross, handmade in silver, which you will nowhere else find in the world, peculiar, originally Coptic, carved in laces, with a name of an artist or a name of a church on it, will come up to see a daylight” (Korabiewicz, 1970 pp. 87ff.). Outside of Addis Ababa (he worked in Gore for some time) Korabiewicz traded by barter with monks, exchanging new iron crosses for old wooden ones (Korabiewicz, 1970 pp. 208ff.). Other crosses he received as gifts for his medical services (Korabiewicz, 1970 p. 138). He also experienced Ethiopians’ special emotional attitude towards crosses when he was expected to return a cross, which he had previously obtained. As a proper collector, he would have done much to make sure that he would not be parted from the object, so eventually he decided to lie and say that the cross had already been sent abroad by post to his sister in Poland (Korabiewicz, 1970 p. 214). When he traded by barter or looked for the objects he wanted to possess, he conversed with monks with the help of his ‘boy’, as he did not speak Amharic himself (Korabiewicz, 1970 p. 208). These meetings were the main source of his knowledge about the crosses he collected. Apart from the information about these conversations we do not know much about how Korabiewicz collected the oral tradition. However, it is still possible to analyse the significance of his findings on the basis of the material he presented in his exhibitions’ catalogues (Korabiewicz,

1966a; Korabiewicz, 1976) and in the monograph about the symbol of a cross (Korabiewicz, 1974).

Korabiewicz spent only two years in Ethiopia in the 1950s, and even though it was not a long period, he developed special feelings for the country. He returned there a number of times in the 1960s and for the last time in 1972.⁵ It was there that he was fascinated with different aspects of Ethiopian art and culture. It was the richness of Ethiopian crosses, their shapes and their symbolical meanings that turned Korabiewicz into a collector, and eventually, into a world-known specialist on the subject. For Korabiewicz himself, his book *Śladami amuletu* ('Following an amulet'), (Korabiewicz, 1974) devoted to the history and symbolism of the sign of the cross was among his most important life achievements, if not the most important. The book was published in Warsaw by Arkady publishing house in 1974. A year before, an English album rich in photographic material presenting different types of crosses was published in Addis Ababa by Holy Trinity Cathedral (Korabiewicz, 1973a). This book is still very popular in Ethiopia and often in use, as will be discussed further in this article.

Among Waław Korabiewicz's reports on the time he spent in Africa, two are dedicated to his Ethiopian experiences. *Eskulap w Etiopii* ('Asclepius in Ethiopia') was published in Warsaw in 1963, and seven years later *Słońce na ambach* ('Sun over ambas'), being a re-written and slightly changed version of the *Asclepius...*, went to Polish bookstores in an edition of thirty thousand volumes. What is interesting, it was also Waław Korabiewicz who undertook the first attempt in Poland to analyse, systematise and describe African objects from the collections of Polish museums with the view to provide basic information on African art (Korabiewicz, 1966b).⁶ It was a ground-breaking work in Poland, and Korabiewicz needed a certain idea of how to present such a broad topic. Eventually, he chose and arranged the objects and their descriptions according to their functions, manners of production and artistic value. As with many others of his ethnographical publications, this one also met critical reactions from professional ethnographers and art historians, but at the same time it was praised as a work dealing with a new and important subject (Bryzek, 2014 pp. 43, 44). A good illustration of how Korabiewicz's work was received by specialists is a review by Jacek Ołędzki⁷ who started his review by writing: "It does not need to be stressed how much knowledge on art of the peoples contemporary living in Africa is neglected in our scholarly interest. (...) In this case the latest work of Waław Korabiewicz should be accepted with great appreciation (...)" (Ołędzki, 1968 p. 542). Ołędzki also praised Korabiewicz, or rather the publishing house and the book itself, for the technical level of publication. He wrote that the album, and most of all the illustrations, "make a very positive impression. In comparison to similar publications of probably most famous English, French and German scholarly centres the Polish one seems to be definitely equal, and even in some parts more interesting and more com-

prehensive" (Ołędzki, 1968 p. 542). However, apart from praising Korabiewicz for undertaking the subject, for using flowery language and the high technical standard of the book, Polish ethnographers criticised the author for concentrating mostly on Warsaw collections and not providing specific data relating to the range of African artefacts in Polish collections. Another objection concerned his methodology, i.e. the lack of information regarding the sources of the author's knowledge (Ołędzki, 1968; Bryzek, 2014, p. 44).

With the exception of the publications in Ethiopia, most of Korabiewicz's books were published only in Poland. Apart from *Safari Mingi*, his travel accounts have never been translated, nor published, outside the country. In terms of international recognition, Korabiewicz's views on the crosses are still being quoted today in works devoted to Ethiopian arts and especially to Ethiopian crosses (as in Hecht, Benzing & Girma Kidane, 1990, Chojnacki, 2006). However, the five-volume *Encyclopaedia Aethiopica* (2003-2014) does not include a separate entry on Korabiewicz, and he is only mentioned three times in other entries.⁸ He is not mentioned in the entry on crosses (Moore, 2003). In Poland today Korabiewicz's books are almost forgotten. However, a small group of those who are interested in African art, and especially in Ethiopian crosses, remember his achievements as a collector both of the artefacts and of the oral tradition.

Korabiewicz's collections of African artefacts

It was extremely important for Waclaw Korabiewicz that the objects he perceived as special and valuable, would be kept in Polish museums. Over the years the strongest ties connected the collector with the National Ethnographical Museum in Warsaw/Państwowe Muzeum Etnograficzne w Warszawie,⁹ but it was Dar es Salaam Museum which was the first he collaborated with. Korabiewicz started to work for the museum when it still functioned under the name of King George V Memorial Museum. He was employed by the institution between 1946 and 1948 and during this period he searched for ethnographical objects for its collection. Later, in 1950, the museum bought forty objects from Korabiewicz. He also chose and bought many artefacts for the American Museum of Natural History in New York and the British Museum in London. However, in Poland it was the exhibition of Ethiopian crosses in the National Museum in Warsaw which got the most attention from the public. It is important to stress that in case of non-Polish museums, Korabiewicz was paid for searching for and obtaining the objects, while in the case of Polish museums, he was only partially compensated for the artefacts, while other objects were donated by him to the museums (Baka-Theis, 2015 p. 115, Bryzek, 2014 pp. 65ff). This related to his patriotic feelings, often stressed by Korabiewicz (Korabiewicz, 1976, p. 5, foreword by Michałowski) and shown by the fact that he sent a container full of objects from Tanganyika to the Ethnographi-

cal Museum in Warsaw in 1954, which caused Korabiewicz to be expelled from Tanganyika (Baka-Theis, 2015 p. 115).

There are three major African collections made by Korabiewicz. The biggest among them is the one in the National Ethnological Museum in Warsaw (Państwowe Muzeum Etnograficzne w Warszawie), which holds circa 1,600 objects. The majority of the artefacts within the collection are masks and everyday objects (among them jewelry, musical instruments and snuff-boxes) from different parts of East and West Africa. The majority of the masks are mapiko helmet masks which were collected among the Makonde people in East Africa. The objects for the Museum were purchased by Korabiewicz over many years which resulted in the creation of a large but not consistent collection. Korabiewicz obtained the artefacts from different corners of the continent. According to the Museum's catalogue the objects came from: Ethiopia and Eritrea (which was one country, i.e. Ethiopia, at the time when Korabiewicz was active), Sudan, Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique and Zanzibar in East Africa, Congo and Zambia in Central Africa, Angola, Ghana, Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Nigeria, Niger, Mali and Ivory Coast in West Africa. There is no permanent exhibition of artefacts from Korabiewicz's collection in the Museum, the objects are displayed every now and then on temporary exhibitions in different Polish museums.¹⁰ The National Ethnographical Museum in Warsaw does not provide an online catalogue or photographs of the objects.

Another collection by Korabiewicz is today held in the American Museum of Natural History in New York. This collection is composed of 551 objects. They are everyday use objects collected from the Jalua, Pare, Kahe, Kwere, Wachaga, Goroa, Mbugwe, Makonde, Mawia, Makua, Wanyaamwezi, Wanyaturu, Wabena and Wazigua peoples in East Africa. The collection increased when the Museum decided to buy from Korabiewicz twenty mapiko masks and a number of masks of another type collected among the Makonde people (Bryzek, 2014 p. 57). Ethiopian crosses are not to be found within this collection. Today, the collection can be viewed online (American Museum of Natural History, 2019).

Among the three, the most consistent and precious collection is the collection of Ethiopian crosses which is held in the National Museum in Warsaw.¹¹ This collection is composed of 405 objects, only some of which are currently on display. The crosses are accompanied by a few other objects and comprise a Collection of Ethiopian Art – there are 450 items of Christian Ethiopian culture in total.¹² Currently, the crosses are exhibited as a part of the Faras Gallery which was reopened in 2015.¹³ In August 2015 twenty Ethiopian crosses from the Korabiewicz collection were to be seen in the National Ethnographical Museum in Warsaw as a part of exhibition "Etiopica w polskich zbiorach" (Aethiopica in Polish collections) (Baka-Theis, 2015 p. 115). The collection from the National Museum in Warsaw is partially photographed and is to be

viewed online on the Museum's website under Collection of Ethiopian Art (Kolekcja sztuki etiopskiej, 2019).

Special features of the collection of Ethiopian crosses from the National Museum in Warsaw

There is no doubt that the collection of Ethiopian crosses from the National Museum in Warsaw is of great historical, artistic and ethnographical value. In 1966 the National Museum in Warsaw organised the exhibition "Masqal - krzyż Etiopii. Wystawa zbiorów Waława Korabiewiczza" (Masqal - cross of Ethiopia. Exhibition of Waław Korabiewicz's collection). At that time it was Korabiewicz's private collection. He designed how the crosses should be exhibited and created a small catalogue (Bryzek, 2014 p. 80). The National Museum in Warsaw and the National Ethnographical Museum cooperated to organise this exhibition. Among circa 300 crosses on display were pectoral crosses, processional crosses and crosses to be carried in the hand (so called hand crosses). They were dated by Korabiewicz to the 12th-20th centuries according to information he obtained from the monks, the previous holders of the crosses, a fact which later evoked some criticisms from the specialists, as not supported by proper scholarly analyses, especially in the field of history of art. The exhibited collection of Ethiopian crosses was accompanied by examples of European crosses which Korabiewicz believed to follow north African patterns (Masłowska, 2006 p. 89, Bryzek, 2014 p. 80). This event inaugurated Korabiewicz's collaboration with the National Museum in Warsaw. In 1975 he donated a part of his collection to the Museum in the form of a perpetual deposit and in 1982 a further ten wooden crosses on the same basis were deposited. Next, fifteen objects¹⁴ including seven Ethiopian crosses and an Ethiopian sistrum were granted to the Museum as a gift in 1989.

As mentioned above, Korabiewicz wrote a catalogue for the 1966 exhibition (Korabiewicz, 1966a) where he provided basic information about Ethiopian crosses, described types of crosses and presented the history and development of different forms of Ethiopian crosses. He also described shapes and origins of the crosses he chose for the exhibition. Basic information regarding the objects on exhibition was also provided in English. Korabiewicz also prepared a more detailed catalogue with Kazimierz Michałowski's¹⁵ foreword for the permanent exhibition in 1976 in Polish and in French (Korabiewicz, 1976).

The agreement of 1966 between Korabiewicz and the Museum regulated different aspects of future exhibitions of the collection. First of all, it was agreed that the collection would be a part of the permanent exhibition under the title "Coptic cross and its imitations". It was also agreed that the permanent exhibition would have a catalogue including all the necessary data and descriptions. Another point of the agreement stated that information about Waław Korabiewicz as the creator of the collection would be provided. The catalogue and

the permanency of the exhibition was so important for Korabiewicz that he made it conditional upon the validity of the agreement. He stressed his wishes in a letter to Professor Kazimierz Michałowski, Director of the Museum at the time (Bryzek, 2014 p. 81, and note 310). In the foreword to the catalogue Professor Michałowski explained that Korabiewicz up until then had “devoted fifteen years of studies and research to this question [of the origin of the motif of the cross], searching in the libraries and monasteries collections in Egypt, Ethiopia and the Balkans [...and this is why] we recognised it to be right to leave without changes Dr. Korabiewicz’s own original concept, as it is something like a path he followed in his attempts as a collector” (Korabiewicz, 1976 p. 6; foreword by Michałowski).

Over the years Korabiewicz took constant care to check if the rules were being followed on how the crosses were exhibited and in which order. He also checked if the information about the crosses was in line with his descriptions and with what he believed to be right.

The agreement between the collector and the Museum as well as the fact that the collection is not the Museum’s property, but a “perpetual deposit”, influenced the fate of the collection over the years. Also Korabiewicz’s confidence in his findings regarding the information about the crosses was of great importance for the future of the collection. He expected the Museum to provide the description of the crosses based exactly on the information collected by himself which was not supposed to be changed in the future. Over the decades the Museum has not been free to dispose of the collection, and unlike to the paintings from Faras, Korabiewicz’s crosses are not displayed and advertised as they could have been according to their attractiveness. As a consequence of the agreement with Korabiewicz, the descriptions in the Museum’s catalogue are still according to his findings, without further verification. The most problematic element, as mentioned above, is the dating provided by Korabiewicz.

When Korabiewicz’s findings started to be questioned (as discussed further in this article) the Museum became reluctant to use his information and the dating of the objects. In 2005 a part of the exhibition was taken down while in 2011 the Faras Gallery was closed for renovation. The renovation was finished in 2015 and since then some of the Ethiopian crosses have been on display again. Today the dating provided by Korabiewicz is hardly convincing, as it seems unlikely that the crosses could be as old as suggested (many of them supposed to be from the 18th and 19th centuries, but a number of crosses much older, with an example of a 13th century cross). Korabiewicz’s information was based on oral information provided by Ethiopian priests and monks, from whom he bought the crosses. As the exact dating of such artefacts is hardly possible¹⁶, and oral information does not prove a fully reliable source, the dating of the collection is a very difficult task, which has not been undertaken so far.

The majority of the crosses in the collection in the National Museum in Warsaw are wooden crosses, which Korabiewicz perceived as being the most attractive. He perceived them “proper”, as they were most commonly used by priests. According to Korabiewicz, iron crosses were already at the time produced mostly for the tourist market and this was why he believed that they were of no cultural or emotional value. A number of crosses from the collection are very attractive in shapes and ornamentation. Some of them are of a very simple form and deserve special attention, as they are not only beautiful items but they are also rare in other collections and not to be seen in Ethiopia nowadays. Among the most attractive artefacts in the collection there is a tabot - an alabaster stone, symbolical copy of the Ark of the Covenant, a table with ten commandments (Korabiewicz, 1976 p. 13, illus. 25). Tabots are the most sacred objects to be kept in Ethiopian churches, the altar stones, which can be seen exclusively by the priests who are allowed to enter the most secret part of the church - *maqdas* (Heldman, 2010 p. 804). The laity is strictly forbidden to see the tabot, hence this object on display in the National Museum in Warsaw is both an interesting item in itself and its exhibition is controversial. However, even though the exhibition was shown to the delegates, including a number of Ethiopian participants, at the International Conference of Ethiopian Studies which took place in Warsaw in 2015, the museum did not experience criticism. Unfortunately, there is no available information as to how Korabiewicz managed to obtain the object, so we are left only to imagine how the sacred object found its way to the rooms of the Warsaw museum. Korabiewicz himself mentioned the tabot in his catalogue of 1976 stressing its role as a secret object, but clearly perceiving it as a mere object of interest when desacralised and presented on display (Korabiewicz, 1976 p. 13). Other artefacts which attract attention are ear cleaners with a sign of a cross, which Korabiewicz believed to be of a special interest, as he found the combination of two functions (religious and hygienic) exceptional and funny (Korabiewicz, 1976 p. 16, illus. 38).

As the majority of the collection is kept in the Museum’s stores, it has not received proper recognition and is not, as it should be, a highlight of the Museum along with the Faras collection.

Impact of Korabiewicz’s work and collections

In 1963 Waław Korabiewicz finished his last contract in Africa, in Ghana, and settled in Poland. He decided to give up his medical career and to concentrate on his work as an ethnographer, based on the material he had collected during the years he spent in Africa.

His attempts to describe African arts and handicrafts were met with great interest in Poland and at the same time with reservations. In Poland in the 1960s and 1970s readers’ interest in distant countries and different cultures

went along with the official political interpretation. Social and political events which accompanied the Year of Africa and the process of constructing independent African countries, in Poland, as was also the case in many other parts of the world, were carefully observed with the hope that the newly shaped continent would have a chance to create states and societies responding to modern, contemporary ideas. In Poland, a part of the Soviet bloc at the time, the African struggle with imperialism was not only carefully observed, but also interpreted in line with official political thought. Polish readers' interest in stories about exotic lands and different customs were thus welcomed by publishers. Additionally, after World War II the fast growing number of Polish intellectuals was in need of knowledge of the world – both in terms of ambitious literature by non-European authors¹⁷ and also in terms of travel literature of different kinds and on a different literary level, including journalists' reports.

Under these conditions, it was not surprising, that books by Waław Korabiewicz describing his experiences and adventures in Africa aroused major interest. It was also characteristic of this period in Poland that the growing need for literature of different kinds was met by huge print runs of the published books. Cheap prices of publications by state-run publishers also made it possible for everybody to buy a book. Korabiewicz's writings, as with many other books published in Poland at the time, were printed in very large numbers. *Eskulap w Etiopii* was printed in over 200,000 copies, *Śladami amuletu* in 10,220 copies. The high number of copies together with demand for such books made Korabiewicz a popular author, and not only his travel reports were commonly read, but also his publications on crosses gained much popularity.

However, as has already been mentioned, his findings on African art and on the symbolism of the cross generally, and on Ethiopian crosses in particular, were met with many reservations from specialists. In particular Korabiewicz's theories on the history and symbolism of the cross were heavily criticised. He was accused of committing a number of serious mistakes as a result of a non-professional attitude, and of creating his own fantastic ideas and explanations instead¹⁸ (Bryzek, 2014 p. 46).

However, apart from the criticism from the specialists, there is no doubt that some of the information concerning Ethiopian crosses which is circulating today, even in Ethiopia, is based on Korabiewicz's findings. A number of publications dealing with the subject of the crosses refer to the classification of Korabiewicz (among others: Chojnacki, 2006, Smolińska, 2008), and also explanation of the symbolism of the different elements is presented according to Korabiewicz's findings (Hecht, Benzing and Girma, 1990 pp. 15ff).

Stanisław Chojnacki in the most complete and reliable work on Ethiopian crosses so far, *Ethiopian crosses: a cultural history and chronology*, does not include

criticism of Korabiewicz, instead when discussing different attempts to classify forms of the crosses he presents also Korabiewicz's classification, which divided crosses into four main categories: "manual-processional" (or: "processional-manual"), manual, processional and pectoral. In the case of one more group consisting of – according to Korabiewicz – "so-called appex or architectural crosses" Chojnacki suggests that they should not have been singled out as a feature belonging exclusively to churches, as in some parts of Tigray lay houses are also decorated with crosses on their rooftops (Chojnacki, 2006 pp. 18,19). Chojnacki also called Korabiewicz an "inventive Polish collector" when referring to a name given by him "to the type of cross strongly reminiscent of a spear [which] was christened 'Longinus' [...] after the name of the soldier who pierced Christ's side at the Crucifixion" (Chonacki, 2006 p. 23 referring to Korabiewicz, 1973a: figs. 40, 62). Korabiewicz also used Ethiopian terms for some types of crosses, i.e. the Havaría¹⁹ and the Kernebege group of crosses²⁰ (Korabiewicz, 1973a). Korabiewicz's contribution in collecting oral tradition on the crosses should be stressed. Stanisław Chojnacki warns that "there is always a degree of uncertainty about whether the informant, usually a scholar of the Ethiopian Church, has given an explanation which has been transmitted from generation to generation and whose veracity is generally accepted or whether he has spontaneously invented it for the occasion. Traditional Church scholars are generally endowed with a rich imagination and, in turn, this may lead to flights of fancy from time to time" (Chojnacki, 2006 p. 79). This is very true also in terms of what Korabiewicz established and should be remembered when analysing Korabiewicz's texts. Nevertheless, even if information collected by Korabiewicz needs to be approached with a critical attitude, it should be recognised that not only did he manage to gather vast quantities of material, but also he did his best to systematise his findings. He was also the first to make an attempt to apply a scholarly attitude to his findings. Even if he partially failed, his work should not be neglected.

In Ethiopia, Korabiewicz's *The Ethiopian Crosses* has been for long one of the most popular books on the subject, still to be bought at the booksellers' stalls and in souvenir/antique shops. This book presents over two hundred photographs of different crosses from Korabiewicz's collection, some photographs of Ethiopian monks wearing crosses and Ethiopian churches and two examples of signs of Coptic crosses (from the British Museum in London and from the Coptic Museum in Cairo) (Korabiewicz, 1973a). Most of the photographs are accompanied by short information regarding the type and special features of the crosses and they also often reveal an emotional attitude of the author towards the beauty and charm of the artefacts, as well as his ideas regarding the origin and meaning of some of the elements. For example the author writes: "these three crosses of unique beauty, with their vegetable decorative motives remind us of their Paradise tree origin" (Korabiewicz, 1973a: fot. 34, pages not numbered), or "most processional crosses are made in metal (...). Wooden versions can be found today in the smaller churches in the heart of

the country. Each has the hollow shaft for the supporter" (Korabiewicz, 1973a: fot. 96, 97), or: "Adam's grave has found a place in the handle of the cross, a reminder of its legendary counterpart under the cross on Golgotha" (Korabiewicz, 1973a: fot. 12). Many of the crosses featured in the volume are now in the collection of The National Museum in Warsaw.

Nowadays in Addis Ababa and Lalibela many of the shopkeepers and tradesmen keep the book with the purpose of proving to the buyers, that the cross on sale is 'traditional'. The findings by Korabiewicz described in this particular book are treated as the best proof that the offered crosses are 'proper' and that they follow the tradition. The information in the book is also used to explain the symbolism of different elements of the cross.²¹ I have also experienced in Lalibela that the same book was not only presented to me as a proof of the 'rightness' of the cross, but also it served to the artisan as a collection of patterns to be followed in order to produce "traditional" crosses.²² This belief shared by the contemporary tradesman (and possibly artisans) not only gave new meaning to Korabiewicz's findings, but also makes an interesting topic for future research, a subject which is beyond the scope of this article²³.

Final remarks

Quite unfortunately, nowadays the majority of the collections built up by Waclaw Korabiewicz is not on display. To a certain extent the collections are also not properly catalogued, and also seem not to be properly appreciated by the museums. In terms of the collection of Ethiopian crosses in the National Museum in Warsaw, most objects are well hidden in the museum's storage, even though this is contrary to the agreement between the museum and Korabiewicz. One of the obstacles in terms of arranging permanent exhibitions is the lack of specialists in Ethiopian art in Poland, however it only underlines the need for international projects to carry out research on the collections. Crosses from the National Museum in Warsaw are waiting patiently for scholars' interest and undoubtedly offer different possibilities for further studies, especially within the history of art, but also in the more general history of Ethiopia. Korabiewicz was fascinated with the development of artistic forms of the Ethiopian cross and how these forms represented the traveling of ideas. All these questions are still valid, the more so since the development of Ethiopian Studies over the last decades and new findings offer new options and directions of further research. Crosses are fine examples of Ethiopian material culture and taking into consideration that the Warsaw collection is one of the biggest in the world, it should not be forgotten by researchers in Ethiopian Studies.

What makes Waclaw Korabiewicz outstanding in terms of his writings as well as a collector, is his passion which is easily to be seen in any of his works. His books including his publications on African art and ethnographical anal-

yses published in a number of journals, were written with zest and eloquence which makes reading them very enjoyable. Nowadays, the books which were written more or less half a century ago have become historical sources, which preserve information about different aspects of life in Ethiopia and other parts of Africa at that time. Discussing Korabiewicz's achievements as a collector we can easily see that this passion gave meaning to his life, a fact which he actually clearly stated in *Safari Mingi* (Korabiewicz, 1959 and further editions). This emotional involvement influenced for better and for worse the fate of the collection of Ethiopian crosses from the National Museum in Warsaw. There is no doubt, however, that these unique objects as well as their collector deserve world recognition and give a rare opportunity to see the beauty of this special art production of Ethiopian Christian culture.

Fig. 1 and 2 Crosses of a simple form from Korabiewicz's collection, National Museum in Warsaw, photography by Zbigniew Doliński.

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Notes

¹ I would like to thank Professor Aleksandra Sulikowska-Bełczowska from the National Museum in Warsaw and Dariusz Skonieczko from the National Ethnographical Museum in Warsaw for their kind support.

² Unfortunately, no biography of Waław Korabiewicz (apart from his autobiography: Korabiewicz, 1973c), has ever been published. Monika Bryzek wrote a B.A. dissertation devoted to Korabiewicz and his African collections, where she presents a lot of interesting material (Bryzek, 2014).

³ Apart from travel reports, Korabiewicz wrote poetry (*Bajki dla dorosłych* (Fairytales for grown-ups) published in 1953, *Rapsod o głowie hetmana* (Rhapsody about Hetman's head) published in 1973 and *Wiersze niemodne* (Unfashionable poems) published in 1992); he collected information on traditional folk medical treatments (among others: *Cuda bez cudów. Rzecz o dziwnych lekach* (Miracles without miracles, being a story about odd medications) published in 1989); wrote three biographies (only one of them published), three books for children (two of them published); and (being himself a dedicated anti-cleric) was a keen researcher on religious studies, writing also on this topic (among others: *Tajemnice młodości i śmierci Chrystusa* (Secrets of Christ's youth and death) which was published in 1992). Korabiewicz wrote also two autobiographies: *Złowiłem życie* ('I caught life') published in 1973 and translated into Czech, and *Pokusy* ('Temptations') about his early life, published in 1986. His first travel book, *Kajakiem do minaretów* ('Kayaking to minarets'), described how he travelled by kayak to Turkey, and this book was published in 1935 (reprinted in 1958).

⁴ Examples of books devoted to Korabiewicz's non-Ethiopian African experiences are: *Kwaheri* dealing with his 1945-1946 journey, first published in 1958 (later reprinted); *Safari Mingi. Wędrówki po Afryce* (Safari Mingi. African journeys) was first published in 1959 (and later reprinted, also translated into Russian and Slovak); *Do Timbaktu* (To Timbaktu) described his trip to West Africa and was published in 1967.

⁵ The documents relating to his journeys are kept in IPN/*Instytut Pamięci Narodowej* (The Institute of National Remembrance) archives, as Korabiewicz was monitored by the government because of his many journeys, as well as his literary and social activities (Bryzek, 2014 p. 28, note 111).

⁶ This book was also published in English (Korabiewicz, 1966c).

⁷ Jacek Ołędzki (1933-2004) was an acclaimed Polish ethnographer and anthropologist of culture (https://pl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jacek_Ołędzki).

⁸ Korabiewicz is mentioned in the entries on art exhibitions, on Ethiopian relations with Poland where he is named as one of the most prominent among individuals who shaped Polish-Ethiopian relations after World War II (Hryćko, 2010 p. 165) and on literature on Ethiopia.

⁹ When Korabiewicz started collaboration with the museum in the 1940s, the name and the location of the museum were different. It was Muzeum Kultur

Ludowych (Museum of Folk Cultures) and was located in Młociny, which is today a part of Warsaw, but at the time was still outside the city.

¹⁰ At the time of writing this article there is an exhibition in the National Ethnographical Museum in Warsaw (Państwowe Muzeum Etnograficzne w Warszawie) 'Technology of Magic' (open from 21 March 2019 until 30 June 2019). Among other artefacts, the exhibition presents a number of Makonde mapiko masks from Korabiewicz's collection (Technology of Magic 2019). Also a permanent African exhibition with an Ethiopian section is planned.

¹¹ Monika Bryzek suggests that this collection is the second biggest in the world, but with no further information (Bryzek, 2014 p. 81). It seems probable that the only bigger collection of Ethiopian crosses would be that in the Museum of the Institute of Ethiopian Studies, Addis Ababa University in Ethiopia.

¹² Apart from Korabiewicz's donation, in the Collection of Ethiopian Art there are artefacts obtained from another Polish renowned scholar of Ethiopian Studies and a collector — Professor Stanisław Chojnacki.

¹³ Faras Gallery (or: The Professor Kazimierz Michałowski Faras Gallery) in the National Museum in Warsaw is a collection of Medieval Nubian paintings from the 8th to the 14th centuries from the cathedral in Faras (kingdom of Nobadia), which was an important urban centre south of the Nile's first cataract. This unique collection is a result of the activity of Polish archeologists led by Kazimierz Michałowski within the international Nubia Campaign, whose aim was to preserve ancient legacies threatened by flooding from the imminent construction of the Aswan High Dam in Egypt in 1960s (Faras Gallery 2019).

¹⁴ The donation included chinaware and ceramics from England, India and Pakistan (Bryzek, 2014 p. 82).

¹⁵ Professor Kazimierz Michałowski (1901-1981) was a Polish archeologist and Egyptologist, precursor of Nubiology and a founder of a Polish school of archeology, a well acclaimed world specialist who led excavations in different parts of the Nile Valley, but also in Myrmekion (Crimea) and Palmyra. Professor Michałowski had great administrative skills which enabled him to establish two Polish permanent research centres in Egypt — one in Cairo, another in Alexandria. He was also very active at the University of Warsaw and Polish Academy of Sciences, where he established institutes of Mediterranean archeology and where he held a number of prestigious functions including pro-rector of the University of Warsaw in the 1940s. For many years he was also a Director of the National Museum in Warsaw.

¹⁶ On chronology of Ethiopian crosses and methodology applied by art historians see: Chojnacki, 2006 pp. 91ff. pp. 99.

¹⁷ Starting from the 1960s a growing number of works of African literature was translated into Polish. The novels were published in huge numbers of copies and achieved much popularity. It was not as popular, however, as South American literature, which was to be found in almost each and every Polish home library in 1970s and 1980s.

¹⁸ These opinions are shared by contemporary art historian. Monika Bryzek in her dissertation quotes a critical review from the 1980s by historian Ewa Wipszycka when deciding about not publishing reprints or new editions of *Śladami amulet* (Bryzek, 2014 p. 46). However, the critical voices appeared in Poland, not internationally, as it seems that the subject aroused such attention only locally.

¹⁹ He wrote: "In Ethiopia the original circular emblem of the Egyptian prior has developed some markedly beautiful and diversified forms of the 'Havaria' group" (Korabiewicz, 1973a: fot. 3, pages not numbered).

²⁰ "The next 'Kernebege' (Horns of the Ram) group of manual crosses opens with this artistic 'blow-up'. The tips of the cross arms are reminiscent of ram's horns of a trefoil" (Korabiewicz, 1973a: fot. 52, pages not numbered).

²¹ This happened to me a number of times during my visits to antique shops, mostly in Addis Ababa, but also in Lalibela and in Aksum on different occasions starting from 2005 and later during my research on antique paintings (Ethiopian modern paintings in traditional style) in 2017 and 2018.

²² Conversation by the author in Lalibela, Ethiopia in 2011.

²³ The same pattern of thinking I experienced in Tunisia, in Sousse, where a French book on traditional Berber pottery was offered to me to prove that the objects on sale were traditional patterns and were 'authentic'. The information was also given, that the patterns are authentic because they are not only made by old ladies, but they are also copied from the book (conversation by the author in Sousse, Tunisia, in 2014).